

Evaluating The Impact Of Cybersecurity Strategy And Implementations In Governmental Institutions In Nigeria

Okeke, G. T., Chaku, S. E., Bassey, S. & Owoicho, P. G.

Centre for Cyberspace Studies, Nasarawa State University Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This research examines the implementation of Nigeria's 2021 National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS) across governmental institutions, focusing on the effectiveness, challenges, and outcomes of its adoption. Employing a mixed-methods design, the study integrates quantitative survey data and qualitative interviews to provide a comprehensive assessment of policy integration, threat management, and institutional readiness. Results reveal inconsistent policy enforcement, limited technical capacity, and uneven resource allocation as key barriers to effective NCSS implementation. Only 27.78% of surveyed institutions reported having fully enforced cybersecurity policies, while over half indicated insufficient funding and shortages of skilled personnel. Despite these challenges, leadership commitment emerged as a positive driver for improved cybersecurity readiness. The study underscores the need for enhanced capacity building, coordinated inter-agency collaboration, and rigorous monitoring to ensure that the NCSS's strategic objectives are effectively operationalized. The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to fortify Nigeria's cybersecurity posture and protect critical national infrastructure.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, National Cybersecurity Strategy, Government Institutions, Policy Implementation, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of technology has made cybersecurity a critical issue for governments, organizations, and individual's worldwide (Balisane et al., 2024). As nations increasingly depend on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for governance, economic development, and public service delivery, they face heightened exposure to cyber threats. This reliance on digital systems leaves governmental institutions vulnerable to cyber risks, including data breaches, ransomware attacks, and large-scale cyber disruptions.

Critical National Information Infrastructure (CNII), which spans essential sectors such as finance, healthcare, energy, and public administration, plays a crucial role in national security. However, the interconnectivity of these systems creates vulnerabilities that cybercriminals can exploit, potentially leading to cascading failures. A proactive cybersecurity approach is necessary to mitigate these risks, focusing on resilience, rapid threat response, and recovery mechanisms (Mbanaso et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, the expansion of ICT and growing internet penetration have introduced both opportunities and cybersecurity challenges. To safeguard its digital landscape, the Nigerian government developed the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS) in 2014, formalized under the Cybercrimes (Prohibition,

Prevention, Etc.) Act of 2015. Recognizing the growing sophistication of cyber threats, the NCSS was revised in 2021 to align with emerging global best practices (Ikuero, 2022).

Ikuero (2022) provides an in-depth analysis of cybersecurity coordination in Nigeria, highlighting the NCSS as a well-structured framework. However, the study reveals inconsistencies in its implementation across governmental institutions, primarily due to weak enforcement mechanisms, limited technical expertise, and inter-agency coordination challenges. Despite these hurdles, the NCSS remains a significant milestone in Nigeria's cybersecurity efforts, laying the groundwork for enhanced digital security. Nevertheless, there is a pressing need to examine how governmental institutions translate these strategic directives into practical implementation.

The updated NCSS is built upon eight key strategic pillars: Strengthening cybersecurity governance, Safeguarding CNII, Enhancing incident management, Improving legal and regulatory frameworks, Strengthening cyber defense capabilities, Supporting a thriving digital economy, Conducting assurance evaluations, Fostering international collaboration. While these pillars aim to enhance national cybersecurity resilience, their implementation across governmental institutions is fraught with challenges. Resource constraints, skill shortages, inconsistent leadership commitment, and inter-agency collaboration difficulties impede effective execution. While some governmental institutions have successfully incorporated the NCSS into their operations, others struggle due to inadequate funding and operational inefficiencies (Riotta et al., 2023). This uneven adoption weakens Nigeria's cybersecurity posture, increasing the risks to critical infrastructure and public services.

Moreover, there is a lack of systematic evaluation of the NCSS's impact on strengthening governmental institutions' cybersecurity preparedness. Ikuero (2022) argues that while the policy framework is in place, the absence of clear enforcement and performance metrics hampers the evaluation of its effectiveness. The study calls for a structured evaluation system to track governmental institutions' compliance and cybersecurity resilience, ensuring that implementation gaps are identified and addressed.

Building upon Ikuero (2022), this study aims to evaluate how governmental institutions in Nigeria integrate the NCSS into their cybersecurity frameworks, evaluate its measurable impact on cybersecurity readiness, and identify the key factors influencing its effectiveness. Specifically, the research will examine governmental institutions' implementation of NCSS principles, evaluate cybersecurity outcomes in areas such as threat detection and risk management, and explore the role of resources, technical expertise, and leadership in shaping cybersecurity success.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several scholars have examined the cybersecurity landscape in Nigeria, focusing on policy gaps, technological limitations, and public awareness deficiencies. Their collective findings reveal significant challenges in implementing the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS), particularly within governmental institutions.

A major challenge facing Nigeria's cybersecurity framework is the lack of a well-coordinated and fully enforced regulatory structure. Osho and Onoja (2015) analyzed the *2014 National Cyber Security Policy and Strategy (NCPS)* and found that, although it adopted a multi-stakeholder approach, its enforcement was weak due to limited collaboration with Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and the absence of a national digital identity framework. Similarly, Nayak and Bello (2024) evaluated the *Cybercrime Act (2015)* and concluded that it does not adequately address evolving threats such as AI-driven cyberattacks, Internet of Things (IoT) vulnerabilities, and ransomware.

Building upon these discussions, Ikuero (2022) conducted a critical review of cybersecurity governance in Nigeria, identifying substantial policy-enforcement challenges within governmental institutions. The study found that, although the NCSS offers a structured approach to cybersecurity, its implementation remains weak due to inadequate inter-agency collaboration, a lack of technical expertise, and outdated ICT infrastructure. Ikuero further emphasized the urgent need for a *National Cybersecurity Coordination Centre (NCCC)* to strengthen policy execution and inter-agency cooperation. However, the study did not conduct an empirical evaluation of NCSS implementation within governmental institutions—a gap that the present research seeks to address.

Comparing Nigeria's cybersecurity framework to international best practices, Temitope and Saheed (2022) examined cybersecurity policies in countries such as the United States, United Kingdom, Estonia, and Israel. Their study found that weak cybersecurity governance in Nigeria continues to hinder national security and recommended the establishment of a centralized cybersecurity agency to improve coordination among governmental institutions. Similarly, Oreoluwa (2022) assessed Nigeria's inability to comply with global cybersecurity standards such as NIST, ISO 27001, and GDPR, concluding that enforcement remains weak due to outdated infrastructure and regulatory shortcomings.

Beyond policy gaps, Nigeria faces significant technological and capacity-building challenges in cybersecurity implementation. Lewis and Alan (2023) conducted a mixed-methods study on cybersecurity challenges within Nigerian governmental institutions, finding that poor inter-agency collaboration, inadequate training, and outdated security protocols hinder effective cybersecurity enforcement. Lain (2023) similarly observed that a shortage of skilled cybersecurity professionals in many government agencies has left them highly vulnerable to cyber threats. Expanding on this issue, Ikuero (2022) identified skill shortages within Nigerian governmental institutions as a major barrier to cybersecurity policy implementation, noting that the lack of continuous cybersecurity training programs has led to low compliance with security protocols in government agencies. These findings align with those of Lewis and Alan (2023), reinforcing the argument that capacity-building initiatives are essential for strengthening Nigeria's cybersecurity resilience.

Workforce development is critical to closing this gap. Saleh AlDaajeh, Ahmed, and Faisal (2022) examined the impact of National Cybersecurity Strategic Plans (NCSPs) on education and proposed a Goal-Question-Outcomes (GQO) model to align cybersecurity curricula with national security objectives. However, their study found that Nigeria has yet to fully integrate cybersecurity education into its training programs, resulting in a persistent shortage of cybersecurity professionals. Additionally, Nigeria's reliance on foreign technologies continues to present significant security risks, particularly in the absence of local cybersecurity innovations and indigenous technological capacity.

Collectively, these studies indicate that while Nigeria has made commendable strides in developing cybersecurity policies and frameworks, persistent challenges remain in enforcement, inter-agency collaboration, workforce development, and technological independence. Therefore, this research addresses these gaps by empirically evaluating the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy within governmental institutions, focusing on policy effectiveness, institutional capacity, and technological readiness toward achieving a resilient national cybersecurity posture.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Framing Research Questions

Formulating precise research questions is essential in investigating cybersecurity governance, especially within the context of national policy implementation. Given the multidimensional nature of cybersecurity and the operational complexities of governmental institutions, the research questions were carefully structured to guide a systematic and empirical assessment of the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS). These questions aim to evaluate the effectiveness, integration, and measurable outcomes of the NCSS implementation across governmental bodies in Nigeria.

This study is therefore designed to answer the following research questions:

- i. What are the key factors influencing the effectiveness of the National Cybersecurity Strategy implementation across governmental institutions?
- ii. How have governmental institutions integrated the National Cybersecurity Strategy into their operations?
- iii. What measurable impact has the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy had on the cybersecurity readiness of governmental institutions?

3.2 Research Design

This study uses a Mixed-Methods Research (MMR) approach to evaluate the implementation and impact of the National Cybersecurity Strategy across Nigerian government institutions. Following a Sequential Explanatory Model, it begins with quantitative data collection and analysis, followed by qualitative data

to clarify the findings. Key factors such as people, processes, and technology, including workforce capacity, policy frameworks, and infrastructure, are examined to identify enablers and barriers to effective cybersecurity.

An Ex-post Facto design allows the evaluation of the strategy's effectiveness after implementation without manipulating variables. Surveys are used in the quantitative phase to reveal trends, while interviews and open-ended responses in the qualitative phase provide deeper insights. This aligns with Ikuero (2022), who supports combining structured and experiential data for greater validity. Grounded in pragmatism and interpretivism, the study integrates objective data with lived experiences. Figure 3.1 illustrates the research design.

Figure 3.1 shows the pictorial representation of the research design for this study.

3.3 Data Collection

The study employs a dual approach to data collection, integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy's implementation. Quantitative data will be collected through surveys distributed among governmental institution personnel, featuring standardized, closed-ended questions that measure key variables related to strategy implementation and facilitate structured analysis. Qualitative data will be gathered through interviews with selected cybersecurity professionals, using open-ended questions to explore implementation challenges and experiences in greater depth. This combined approach ensures that the study captures both measurable patterns and contextual insights, providing a well-rounded understanding of the strategy's impact.

3.4 Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

The study population comprises government officials, IT professionals, and cybersecurity personnel within governmental institutions responsible for implementing Nigeria's National Cybersecurity Strategy. A total sample of 120 participants is selected, with 20 individuals drawn from each of six governmental institutions. The sampling process follows a two-stage approach: stratified random sampling in the quantitative phase to ensure representation based on governmental institution type, job role, and cybersecurity involvement, and purposive sampling in the qualitative phase to select participants with direct expertise in cybersecurity for interviews and open-ended survey questions. To enhance the credibility of the findings, the survey instrument (AINCSIMDA) will undergo pilot testing with 10

participants (10% of the total sample). A reliability test using Cronbach’s Alpha will assess internal consistency, and refinements will be made based on pilot feedback to improve clarity and validity.

3.5 Techniques for Data Analysis and Model Specification

This study adopts a sequential explanatory mixed-methods approach to evaluate the implementation and impact of the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS) in Nigerian governmental institutions.

Quantitative data are analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean) to summarize implementation patterns, and Pearson Correlation to examine relationships between variables such as policy execution, training, and institutional readiness. These variables align with key NCSS domains like governance, incident management, and legal frameworks.

Qualitative data from open-ended responses and interviews are analyzed thematically. This involves coding and categorizing responses to identify patterns related to implementation gaps, leadership, capacity constraints, and awareness.

The model specification links implementation, impact, and challenges to research objectives. Independent variables such as policy adoption and training are mapped to outcomes like cybersecurity readiness and threat response. This combined analysis ensures a comprehensive evaluation of NCSS execution and informs targeted recommendations for improving cybersecurity policy across governmental institutions.

3.6 Justification of Methods

The methods selected for this study are both scientifically rigorous and contextually appropriate for evaluating cybersecurity policy implementation. A Mixed-Methods Research (MMR) approach, specifically the Sequential Explanatory Model, is employed to combine the strengths of quantitative and qualitative data. This design allows initial patterns from survey responses to be further explained through qualitative insights, enhancing the depth and credibility of the findings. As supported by Ikuero (2022), this approach promotes triangulation and strengthens the validity of cybersecurity research.

The Ex-Post Facto Design is adopted to evaluate the real-world impact of the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS) without manipulating variables—an appropriate choice for policy evaluation studies. Stratified sampling ensures diverse representation across governmental institutions, while purposive sampling targets cybersecurity personnel for rich, expert-level input. Quantitative data are analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to measure strategy implementation and outcomes, while thematic analysis captures recurring issues and stakeholder experiences. This combination supports a comprehensive and reliable evaluation of NCSS implementation in the Nigerian public sector.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Presentation

4.2.1 **Data Analysis on Research Question 1:** *What are the key factors influencing the effectiveness of the National Cybersecurity Strategy implementation across governmental institutions?*

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics Summary for Research Question 1: What are the key factors influencing the effectiveness of the National Cybersecurity Strategy implementation across governmental institutions?

Item	Statement	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)
1	My governmental Institution has sufficient financial resources allocated for cybersecurity initiatives.	54.00%	50.00%
2	The shortage of skilled cybersecurity personnel limits my governmental Institution’s ability to implement NCSS effectively.	41.70%	58.30%
3	Cybersecurity policies in my governmental Institutions are strictly enforced and regularly reviewed for compliance.	49.10%	50.90%

4	There is a lack of accountability in enforcing cybersecurity policies within my governmental Institutions.	52.80%	47.20%
5	International cybersecurity standards (e.g., ISO 27001, NIST) are incorporated in my governmental Institution’s framework.	50.90%	49.10%
6	Leadership support in my governmental Institution has played a crucial role in ensuring NCSS compliance.	47.20%	52.80%
7	Cybersecurity audits are rarely conducted in my governmental Institutions to evaluate NCSS compliance.	49.10%	50.90%
8	The enforcement of data protection policies within my governmental Institutions aligns with NCSS requirements.	49.00%	50.90%
Average Percentage		49.23%	51.26%

According to the results presented in Table 4.1 and chart 1, the most prominent factors influencing the effectiveness of NCSS implementation across governmental institutions include skills shortages, weak leadership support, and limited adoption of international standards. Specifically, 58.3% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that the shortage of skilled cybersecurity personnel significantly hinders the execution of NCSS mandates. Similarly, 52.8% acknowledged that inadequate leadership support impacts compliance efforts, while 50.9% indicated that their organizations have not integrated recognized international cybersecurity frameworks such as ISO 27001 or NIST. These results reinforce the conclusion by Ikuero (2022), who argued that policy-practice gaps are often exacerbated by institutional capacity deficits and governance weaknesses, which directly affect policy enforcement and sustainability.

Table 4.2. The Pearson correlation analysis between C3 (“Cybersecurity policies in my governmental Institutions are strictly enforced and regularly reviewed for compliance”) and C7 (“Cybersecurity audits are rarely conducted in my governmental Institution to evaluate NCSS compliance”)

		C3	C7
C3: Cybersecurity policies in my governmental Institutions are strictly enforced and regularly reviewed for compliance.	Pearson correlation	1	-.355**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	108	108
C7: Cybersecurity audits are rarely conducted in my governmental Institutions to evaluate NCSS compliance.	Pearson correlation	-.355**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	108	108

Table 4.2 shows the Pearson correlation analysis between **C3** (“Cybersecurity policies in my governmental institution are strictly enforced and regularly reviewed for compliance”) and **C7** (“Cybersecurity audits are rarely conducted in my governmental institution to evaluate NCSS compliance”) revealed a statistically significant moderate negative relationship ($r = -0.355$, $p = 0.000$, $N = 108$). This suggests that as the enforcement and regular review of cybersecurity policies increase within governmental institutions, there is a corresponding decrease in the frequency of reported lapses in cybersecurity audits. In other words, governmental institutions with stronger policy enforcement tend to conduct cybersecurity audits more regularly. The statistical significance of the correlation indicates that this relationship is unlikely due to chance, highlighting the potential role of proactive policy management in ensuring ongoing compliance with the NCSS through consistent audit practices.

4.2.2 Data Analysis on Research Question 2: How have governmental institutions integrated the National Cybersecurity Strategy into their operations?

Table 4.3: Descriptive Statistics Summary for Research Question 2: How have governmental institutions integrated the National Cybersecurity Strategy into their operations?

Statements	Yes (%)	No (%)
My governmental institution has an officially documented IT or cybersecurity policy.	48.10%	51.90%
The existing IT/cybersecurity policy in my governmental institution aligns with the NCSS.	48.10%	51.90%
My governmental institution does not have a formal cybersecurity policy, but plans are in place to develop one.	51.90%	48.10%
Cybersecurity policies within my governmental institution are fully aligned with NCSS guidelines.	49.10%	50.90%
There is a designated cybersecurity unit responsible for enforcing IT and cybersecurity policies in my governmental institution.	43.50%	56.50%
There are structured guidelines within my governmental institution to integrate NCSS principles effectively.	50.00%	50.00%
Interdepartmental collaboration on cybersecurity matters has improved due to NCSS implementation.	46.30%	53.70%
Cybersecurity-related decisions in my governmental institution are primarily made without reference to NCSS directives.	54.60%	45.40%
Average Percentage	48.95%	51.05%

The results in Table 4.3 and chart 2 strongly mirror the findings of Ikuero (2022): while the NCSS exists and awareness may be growing, actual integration across governmental institutions remains inconsistent and largely superficial. Only 48.1% of governmental institutions have formal IT or cybersecurity policies that align with the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS), revealing a considerable policy implementation gap. Moreover, 56.5% of the governmental institutions lack dedicated cybersecurity units, and 50% do not have clear or structured guidelines for integrating the NCSS into their operations. In addition, 54.6% of cybersecurity-related decisions are made without referencing NCSS directives, underscoring the limited influence of the strategy on decision-making processes within these institutions

Table 4.4: The Pearson correlation between B1 (My governmental Institution has an officially documented IT or cybersecurity policy) and B2 (The existing IT/cybersecurity policy in my governmental Institution aligns with the NCSS)

		B1	B2
B1: My governmental institution has an officially documented IT or cybersecurity policy.	Pearson correlation	1	-0.107**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.257
	N	108	108
B2: The existing IT/cybersecurity policy in my governmental institution aligns with the NCSS.	Pearson correlation	-0.107**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.257	
	N	108	108

Table 4.4 represents the Pearson correlation between B1 and B2 was -0.107, with a p-value of 0.257 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the relationship between the two variables is very weak and not statistically significant. This implies that there is no meaningful linear relationship between the two aspects of the National Cybersecurity Strategy implementation measured by B1 and B2. The result suggests that

governmental Institutions may be implementing strategy components independently, without coordinated or interrelated actions.

4.2.3 Data Analysis on Research Question 3: What measurable impact has the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy had on the cybersecurity readiness of governmental institutions?

Table 4.5: Descriptive Statistics Summary for Research Question 3: What measurable impact has the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy had on the cybersecurity readiness of governmental institutions?

Item	Statement	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)
1	My governmental institutions has significantly improved its cybersecurity infrastructure.	42.6%	57.5%
2	Cybersecurity risks and incidents have decreased in my governmental institution due to NCSS implementation.	45.40%	54.70%
3	Regular cybersecurity risk evaluations are conducted in my governmental institution as part of NCSS implementation.	46.30%	53.70%
4	My governmental institution lacks a structured mechanism to measure the success of NCSS implementation.	52.80%	47.20%
5	Cybersecurity awareness and training programs have improved due to NCSS.	40.80%	59.30%
6	My governmental institution struggles to enforce NCSS measures due to lack of resources.	43.50%	56.50%
7	The NCSS has strengthened my governmental institution’s ability to respond to cybersecurity incidents.	39.80%	60.00%
8	My governmental institution lacks a clearly defined incident response plan despite NCSS guidelines.	50.90%	49.10%
9	NCSS has improved inter-agency collaboration on cybersecurity threats.	37.90%	60.00%

Table 4.5 and chart 3 shows that a significant portion of the respondents indicated limited progress in cybersecurity readiness following the implementation of the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS). Specifically, 57.5% reported no substantial improvement in their cybersecurity infrastructure, suggesting persistent gaps in technical capacity. Additionally, 52.8% of governmental institutions revealed that they lack effective mechanisms to evaluate or measure the success of NCSS initiatives. Furthermore, 59.3% observed no noticeable enhancement in cybersecurity training programs since the introduction of the strategy, pointing to deficiencies in workforce development and continuous learning. This supports the findings of Ikuero (2022), who emphasized the existence of a policy-practice gap, where robust national policies often fail to translate into tangible institutional change due to weak enforcement, poor tracking mechanisms, and inadequate resourcing.

Table 4.6: The Pearson correlation analysis between D5 (“Cybersecurity awareness and training programs have improved due to NCSS”) and D8 (“My governmental institution lacks a clearly defined incident response plan despite NCSS guidelines”)

		D5	D8
D5: Cybersecurity awareness and training programs have improved due to NCSS.	Pearson correlation	1	0.223**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.021
	N	108	108
D8: My governmental institution lacks a clearly defined incident response plan despite NCSS guidelines.	Pearson correlation	0.223**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.021	
	N	108	108

The Pearson correlation analysis between D5 (“Cybersecurity awareness and training programs have improved due to NCSS”) and D8 (“My governmental institution lacks a clearly defined incident response plan despite NCSS guidelines”) revealed a statistically significant positive but weak relationship ($r = 0.223$, $p = 0.021$, $N = 108$). This suggests that as cybersecurity awareness and training programs improve within governmental institutions, there is also a slight tendency for these institutions to acknowledge a lack of clearly defined incident response plans, despite NCSS guidelines. Although the relationship is weak, the significance level indicates it is not due to chance. This finding highlights a potential gap in the implementation of the NCSS—while awareness and training efforts are progressing, they may not be sufficiently supported by structured and actionable incident response planning.

4.2.4 Qualitative Findings: Thematic Analysis

A thematic analysis of the interview data revealed six key themes: Implementation Gaps, Capacity Constraints, Leadership and Governance, Awareness and Communication, Security Improvements, and Recommendations for Action. These themes offer insights into the integration, impact, and influencing factors of the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS) implementation in governmental institutions.

Table 4.41: Defined Themes and Descriptions

Theme	Definition / Description	Codes Grouped
Implementation Gaps	Incomplete or early-stage policy execution across governmental institutions.	Partial Implementation, Draft Only, No Formal Program
Capacity Constraints	Challenges with training frequency, coverage, and staff expertise.	No Training, Infrequent Training, Only Tech Trained
Leadership Governance	& Weak top-level commitment, poor coordination, or resistance between units.	Weak Leadership, Resistance, Bureaucratic Delays
Awareness Communication	& Limited awareness campaigns and lack of cross-departmental communication.	No Awareness Campaigns, Internal Disconnect
Security Improvements	Evidence of improvements like better incident response or risk evaluation.	Improved Reporting, Structured Risk Evaluation
Recommendations	Concrete suggestions offered for improving NCSS adoption and governmental Institution performance.	Budget, Training, Mandates, Vendor Enforcement

i. Implementation Gaps

Several participants described partial or inconsistent implementation of the NCSS across their agencies. While some governmental institutions had drafted policies or developed compliance tools, actual enforcement and operational integration remained limited.

“The policy was drafted, but enforcement has been slow and inconsistent.” – Interviewee 1
 “A compliance checklist was piloted in just two departments. It’s not widespread yet.” – Interviewee 10
 “Honestly, I’m not sure we have any formal NCSS program in place.” – Interviewee 3

This theme directly addresses Research Question 1: How have governmental institutions integrated the National Cybersecurity Strategy into their operations? It shows that while there is some level of integration, it varies significantly across governmental institutions, often limited to planning stages without full execution.

ii. Capacity Constraints

Training gaps and lack of skilled personnel emerged as major barriers. Many respondents noted that cybersecurity training was infrequent, limited to technical staff, or absent for administrative personnel.

“Only the technical staff have received any cybersecurity training.” – Interviewee 1
 “I attended just one external workshop in the past year.” – Interviewee 9
 “No formal training is offered to administrative staff.” – Interviewee 6

This theme relates to both Research Question 2 and Research Question 3 by highlighting the lack of measurable improvements in readiness due to limited human capacity and inadequate training, which also act as key influencing factors in NCSS implementation.

iii. Leadership and Governance

The data revealed that top-level support, interdepartmental coordination, and timely decision-making are critical challenges. Several interviewees mentioned bureaucratic delays, lack of clear mandates, and resistance from non-IT units.

“There’s little commitment from leadership to support NCSS adoption.” – Interviewee 8
 “We often face resistance from departments that are not IT-focused.” – Interviewee 4
 “Everything takes too long because of bureaucratic procedures.” – Interviewee 9

This theme addresses Research Question 3, pointing to leadership engagement and governance inefficiencies as major determinants of the success or failure of NCSS implementation.

iv. Awareness and Communication

There is a communication gap regarding the NCSS among non-technical staff. Some participants noted a general lack of internal awareness campaigns or poor interdepartmental information flow.

“There are no internal campaigns to educate the rest of the staff.” – Interviewee 5

“I don’t think HR and IT are on the same page about cybersecurity roles.” – Interviewee 6

“The communication between departments on this issue is very weak.” – Interviewee 3

This theme affects Research Question 1 and Research Question 3, showing that limited awareness and poor communication reduce the effectiveness of the strategy’s integration and create barriers to broader adoption.

v. Security Improvements

Despite the challenges, some governmental institutions reported specific gains such as improved incident reporting, access control, or phishing response. These point to measurable indicators of cybersecurity readiness improvement.

“We’re now able to respond to phishing incidents much faster.” – Interviewee 8

“There’s been a notable decrease in minor security breaches.” – Interviewee 10

“We’ve seen minor improvements in how access controls are applied.” – Interviewee 1

This directly answers Research Question 2, providing evidence of positive cybersecurity outcomes in agencies that have moved beyond planning to partial or full implementation.

vi. Recommendations for Action

Participants proposed actionable strategies for improving NCSS implementation, including increased funding, mandatory cross-departmental training, executive-level enforcement, and hiring specialized personnel.

“The government should increase the cybersecurity budget and enforce clear timelines.” – Interviewee 1

“We need executive mandates that force all departments to comply.” – Interviewee 4

“More scholarships and recruitment of experts would help.” – Interviewee 10

This theme addresses Research Question 3, offering insight into perceived solutions that could enhance the strategy’s effectiveness.

The thematic findings reveal that while there is progress in some governmental institutions, implementation remains fragmented, capacity and communication gaps persist, and governance structures need strengthening. However, measurable improvements in cybersecurity practices are visible where the NCSS is better integrated. These themes help answer the study’s research questions by painting a comprehensive picture of the current state, challenges, and potential for improving national cybersecurity strategy adoption across governmental institutions.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study set out to evaluate how governmental institutions have implemented the National Cybersecurity Strategy (NCSS), the degree of its impact on their cybersecurity posture, and the key factors influencing effective execution. The findings suggest a moderate level of awareness but limited implementation, revealing significant institutional and strategic gaps.

Data from Table 4.17 and other subsections revealed that less than half of the respondents affirmed the existence of a formal cybersecurity policy or its alignment with NCSS guidelines in their organizations. Only 43.5% indicated the presence of a designated cybersecurity unit. This reflects institutional weaknesses and policy disconnections—challenges that Ikuero (2022) clearly identified in his review of Nigeria’s cybersecurity landscape. According to him, the absence of consistent enforcement and centralized coordination has led to uneven implementation of NCSS principles, particularly at the agency level.

The responses to Research Question 2 highlighted a low to moderate perception of NCSS’s impact on improving cybersecurity within governmental institutions. This outcome aligns with Lewis & Alan (2023), who observed that Nigerian governmental institutions continue to suffer from outdated

infrastructure and poor inter-agency collaboration, limiting their ability to respond to evolving threats. Similarly, Ikuero (2022) emphasized that although the NCSS provides a comprehensive policy framework, its effects are muted by the lack of implementation capacity, underfunding, and inconsistent leadership commitment.

A dominant theme across the responses was the lack of trained cybersecurity professionals and formal capacity-building programs. Respondents noted limited investment in technical training or skill development initiatives. This corroborates Osho and Onoja (2015), who concluded that Nigeria's cybersecurity policy efforts were undermined by the absence of a skilled workforce and training institutes, a concern echoed in Ikuero (2022), who called for the urgent establishment of a National Cybersecurity Training Institute (NCTI) to address this gap.

The study also found that interdepartmental collaboration and reference to NCSS directives in decision-making were minimal. This is consistent with Alabi (2024) and Kifordu et al. (2019), who highlighted the lack of cohesive collaboration between government agencies and private cybersecurity stakeholders. Ikuero (2022) also argued that the absence of a National Cybersecurity Coordination Centre (NCCC) is a critical bottleneck that limits cross-agency synergy and slows down national cybersecurity program execution.

Responses further indicated that governmental institutions are not effectively leveraging cybersecurity policies to support Nigeria's digital transformation goals. The NCSS pillar focused on promoting a thriving digital economy was among the least implemented. As noted in Ikuero (2022), failure to embed cybersecurity into the foundation of digital governance risks undermining public trust and the sustainability of digital public services.

The findings of this study reinforce the conclusions reached by Ikuero (2022) and other scholars that Nigeria's cybersecurity posture is constrained by policy-practice gaps, skill shortages, limited funding, and structural coordination failures. While the National Cybersecurity Strategy offers a strong foundation, its uneven integration across governmental institutions hampers its effectiveness.

For the NCSS to deliver on its objectives, there must be stronger enforcement mechanisms, improved inter-agency collaboration, continuous staff development, and the establishment of enabling institutions such as the NCCC and NCTI. Only then can Nigeria achieve a cohesive and resilient national cybersecurity ecosystem.

5. CONCLUSION

The National Cybersecurity Strategy provides a vital framework for strengthening cybersecurity governance within Nigeria's governmental institutions. Its implementation has resulted in tangible improvements, including the establishment of cybersecurity policies, capacity-building initiatives, and enhanced inter-agency coordination. By employing a triangulated mixed-methods approach, this study ensures a robust evaluation that captures both quantitative patterns and qualitative insights, thereby enhancing the reliability of the conclusions drawn.

However, despite these gains, many institutions have not fully integrated the NCSS into their operational frameworks, limiting its potential impact. This inconsistency reflects systemic issues such as resource limitations, inadequate leadership commitment, and fragmented governance structures. To achieve the strategy's objectives, Nigeria must strengthen leadership engagement, secure adequate funding, invest in continuous professional development, and foster a culture of cybersecurity awareness across governmental institutions.

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